

Inferring Missing Entity Identifiers from Context using Event Knowledge Graphs

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Abstract. Complete event data is essential to perform rich analysis. However, real-life systems might fail in recording the (correct) case identifiers the system has operated on, resulting in incomplete event data. We aim to infer missing case identifiers of events by considering the physical constraints of the process which previous work has failed to do. We extended Event Knowledge Graphs (EKGs) with concepts for context and rule-based inference. We use the extended EKGs to model event data in its physical context and define five inference rules to infer identifiers of physical objects in a process. We evaluate the effectiveness of the rules on data from the IC manufacturing industry using conformance checking. Initially, none of the traces were complete. Our method inferred a case identifier for 95% of the events resulting in 88% complete traces.

Keywords: Log repair · Event Knowledge Graph · Modeling · Inference Rule · Contextual Information · Physical Constraints

1 Introduction

Business Process Analytics (BPA) is an area of data analytics that facilitates rich analysis of the way in which business processes work, providing insight into how business processes can be improved. BPA techniques rely on event logs that record the events that happened in the business process, along with (the identifier of) the case to which they belong and the moment in time at which they happened, possibly extended with other information. However, in real-life systems the data in the event logs may be incomplete [20]. Consequently, before event data can be used for BPA, missing data must be added or incomplete events must be removed. If missing data can somehow be *inferred* from the context of the events, that is preferred, because it leads to more usable data to work with. This work focuses on inferring missing case identifiers, also known as the “event-case correlation” problem [5].

Several methods exist to infer missing case identifiers from context. The dominant context information that these methods use for inferring case identifiers is a process model [13,18]. This has some clear drawbacks. Firstly, a process model may not exist or may be hard to create, for example in multi-entity processes [11] or in case the data is at a different level of abstraction than the level at which

the process is understood. Secondly, inference for cyclic processes either requires further context information, such as constraints on time [4] or data [5], which may not be available either, or it may require time-consuming iterations [6] to do the inference. Thirdly, most existing methods only connect the incomplete information to the context information within the algorithm. Only [6] makes the connection between data and context available for further analysis.

To alleviate these problems, we aim to develop techniques for inferring missing identifiers *without* relying on a process model. This paper focuses on inferring missing case identifiers for *processes with batching* where *context* information is available about the handling of *physical objects*. Since these objects are bound by the laws of physics, information about them can be used in combination with simple physics rules to infer other information. For example, if a physical object is in one place in one event and in another place in another event, it must have been moved in between and a movement event must have involved this object.

We propose to use *knowledge graphs* (KGs) for such inference. A KG combines a graph-based representation of data and its context with an inference mechanism [7]. Specifically, translating an incomplete event log into an (incomplete) *Event Knowledge Graph* (EKG) [11] models which events are known to relate to which entities. The problem now is to infer missing relations between events and entities (instead of a global case) which also allows inference for processes with batching. EKGs [11] currently lack concepts for context and inference.

This paper extends EKGs with context information about the process and a pattern-based inference mechanism over this context to infer missing identifiers (relations between events and entities). We demonstrate how to define context in terms of the physical context of events (locations of activities and their handling of physical objects) and how to define inference rules that encode constraints for objects based on the physical context of events.

We implemented and evaluated the technique on an industrial case study with NXP Semiconductors by showing that it can be used to infer missing entity identifiers. Using our method on event data of 7250 events, where 86% of the events lacked an entity identifier, we could infer an identifier for 95% of the events within 30 seconds. Subsequent conformance checking against a normative process model validated the correctness of the inferred identifiers.

Against this background, the remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The related work is discussed in Sect. 2. The problem is elaborated on in Sect. 3 along a running example. Sect. 4 describes a method for inferring identifiers from context using an EKG. Sect. 5 shows the proposed method by creating inference rules for the running example and industrial use case and validates the inference using conformance checking. The findings are discussed in Sec. 6.

2 Related Work

Data-driven process analysis defines minimal requirements for event logs [14]: each event contains at least an activity, timestamp and a case identifier. However, in practice, collected event data might not meet these requirements.

Table 1. Overview of types of (incomplete) data

Timestamp	Activity	Case Identifier	Context Knowledge used for Inference
-	✓	✓	timing information [19,12]
✓	-	✓	other attributes to activities [15,23,2]
✓	✓	-	acyclic process model [13,18]; process model + add. constraints [4,5]; process model + sim. annealing [6]; surrogate id [17]; activity properties [this]

Event data quality issues are assessed in terms of missing or incorrectly recorded attribute values. These typically manifest themselves in systematic “imperfection patterns” [20] due to imperfect data recording mechanisms. Accordingly, specific techniques have been proposed to detect if such data quality ‘patterns’ exist in an event log [1] and to repair them. Repairing data enables us to apply techniques that require complete data such as rich analysis techniques and traceability.

Assuming correct activity and case attributes have been identified [3,16], we focus on *missing values* for the standard attributes of case/object identifier, activity, and timestamp. Existing literature infers missing values for one of the attributes based on information in the other attributes and *additional context knowledge* as summarized in Tab. 1.

Missing timestamps can be inferred by using knowledge of duration of process steps, both, for isolated cases [19] and cases processed via shared resources and queues [12]. *Missing activities* can be inferred by knowledge of how events with specific data attributes in a specific behavioral context relate to activities, e.g., by aggregating low-level observations to activities [15,23] or matching text attributes to activity descriptions [2].

Missing case identifiers are typically inferred by leveraging control-flow knowledge. Existing techniques use a given acyclic probabilistic Markov model [13] or first estimate a model of an acyclic process from an incomplete log and then infer case identifiers [18]. Inferring identifiers for cyclic processes not only requires a process model, but also additional timing constraints [4], data constraints [5], or multiple iterations of matching, e.g., through simulated annealing [6] that also generate rules for correlating events to cases based on the activity, event properties, and their immediate context. No process model is required when a surrogate identifier such as the user in a clickstream is present [17]. A common trait of all techniques is that they assume isolated cases (no batching) and the context knowledge is kept separate from the incomplete event data and reconciled within the algorithmic technique itself.

This paper addresses the problem of inferring missing entity identifiers in processes *with batching* but *without* leveraging a process model defining the control-flow or surrogate identifiers. Instead, we focus on processes handling *physical objects* and use knowledge on the activities themselves and the context the activities operate in to infer entity identifiers.

The problem of inferring missing identifiers is a subproblem of *knowledge inference* addressed by *knowledge graphs* (KGs). A KG thereby consist of (i) a semi-structured graph modeling data and/or knowledge, (ii) a set of inference rules over this graph; applying the rules on the initial graph results in (iii) a derived graph describing derived knowledge [7]. “Semi-structured” means a KG can be flexibly extended with new concepts. *Event Knowledge Graphs* [11] allow to model relations between events and (identified) entities of a process, and allow to describe processes with multiple objects and batching. This makes them a suitable model for our problem (inferring missing identifiers in processes with batching, without a given model). As EKGs as defined in [11] lack concepts for describing a process context and an inference mechanism, we will propose these in Sect. 4.

3 Missing Identifiers in Processes with Physical Objects

We illustrate the problem of identifying from incomplete data which physical objects in a process suffered from errors. We show by a simple example that existing inference techniques fail to reliably infer correct entity identifiers for processes with physical objects and batching. We illustrate how we can reliably infer entity identifiers when applying contextual knowledge about activities, physical objects, and how they are constrained. Then, we state the specific problem together with the expected in- and output.

Notation on Event Data. We first recall some notation on event data over multiple identifiers, i.e., object-centric event data, based on [11]. We write Val for the universe of values, including disjoint sets of activity names and timestamps $Act, Time \subseteq Val$. $Time$ is totally ordered by \leq .

An *event table with entities* (i.e., object-centric log) $T = (E, Attr, Ent, \#)$ consists of events E , attributes $\{act, time\} \subseteq Attr$, entity type attributes $\emptyset \neq Ent \subseteq Attr$, and partial attribute value function $\# : E \times Attr \rightarrow Val$ assigning $e \in E$ and $a \in Attr$ value $\#_a(e) = v$ ($\#_a(e) = \perp$ if a is undefined for e) with $\#_{time}(e) \in Time$ and $\#_{act}(e) \in Act$ are defined.

An event e may have a multi-valued attribute $\#_a(e) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$ (set) or $\#_a(e) = \langle v_1, \dots, v_n \rangle$ (list) for example for events referring to multiple objects; and we write $v_i \in \#_a(e)$. For uniform notation, we also write $v \in \#_a(e)$ for single-valued $\#_a(e) = v$.

In the generalized setting of object-centric or multi-entity processes [11] a trace is defined in relation to an entity identifier. Let $ent \in Ent$ be an entity type. The entity identifiers of type $ent \in T$ are $ent(T) = \{n \mid n \in \#_{ent}(e), e \in E\} \setminus \{\perp\}$. Let $n \in ent(T)$ be an entity identifier. An *entity trace* of n is a sequence $\pi_n = \langle e_1 \dots e_k \rangle$ of events $\{e_1 \dots e_k\} = \{e \in E \mid n \in \#_{ent}(e)\}$ ordered by $\#_{time}(e_i) \leq \#_{time}(e_j)$ for $1 \leq i < j \leq k$. In the following, we specifically discuss (identifiers of) entities that are *physical objects*, e.g., a box.

Running Example. Fig. 1 shows a process, modeled as a proclat [12] (bottom), and the *context* it is executed in, i.e., the physical environment (top). There are

Fig. 1. A process model (proclets [12]) of assembly lines where boxes in a tray are filled, sealed, and labeled (bottom) together with the physical context (top).

two *Assembly Lines* at which *Boxes* are filled and sealed. A *Tray of Boxes*, i.e. a batch, is loaded into an *Assembly Line* if it is *Empty*, then each *Box* individually passes several stations and finally the *Tray* is unloaded from the *Assembly Line*. The first station is the *Fill Station*, at which a *Box* is loaded, filled and unloaded. The second station is the *Seal Station* at which a *Box* is loaded, sealed and unloaded. *Loading* and *Unloading* of the stations is done by a robot arm that needs to be aware of the *Position* of the *Box* in the *Tray*.

Only when *Sealing*, each *Box* is labeled making it uniquely identifiable. Hence only *Seal* events record an entity identifier for the box. Further, *Load* and *Unload* events register per station the *Position* of a *Box* in the *Tray*. For instance, processing three boxes results in the *incomplete* log shown in Fig. 2 where attribute b records the box identifier and p the position in the tray. No event records, both, b and p . Fig. 2(a) visualizes this incomplete log as a *Performance Spectrum* with each color referring to a different box, i.e., blue refers to b_1 , orange to b_2 and green to b_3 [9]. Note that no complete traces of boxes can be constructed.

Suppose a *Filling* error occurred at e_3 . We cannot determine which box was affected by the error on the incomplete log. As a result, an operator has to inspect and possibly even discard the entire *Tray*. To mitigate this problem, we have to obtain complete traces by inferring the likely values for b .

Using control-flow models as context knowledge, e.g., [13,18] allows to infer unknown value $\#_b(e_i)$ from known value $\#_b(e_j)$ when e_j directly precedes or succeeds e_i ; e.g., infer $\#_b(e_9) = b_1$ from $\#_b(e_{10}) = b_1$. Existing technique fail to address the physical constraints and batching (boxes in trays) in our example. The method of [18] generates multiple possible solutions of box id values and traces (depending on parameters), two are shown in Fig. 2(b) and (c): besides the analyst having to pick a solution, the method wrongly relates e_1 and e_{20} to only a single box and wrongly claims b_1 went through filling and sealing first, while the log shows that the box at $p = 2$ was filled first and sealed second.

Physical Constraints and Context. In contrast, Fig. 2(d) visualizes the complete traces of the three boxes in line with the process' context and its (physical) constraints. We note three basic (physical) principles that hold for this process: (P1) for a physical object to be present at/removed from a location, the physi-

Fig. 2. A small log with missing identifiers: observed events with missing entity identifiers (a), behaviors found with a control-flow method (b, c) and correct behavior (d).

cal load/unload activity of that location must have involved this physical object; (P2) activities are performed at physical locations (stations) and the physical object they operate on must be at that location; (P3) physical objects that are consistently kept at the same (relative) spatial location can consistently be distinguished from each other (e.g. positions in the tray/on a conveyor belt). Applying these principles does *not* require a process model, but context information on activities: (C1) which activities process which kind of physical objects at which locations, (C2) which physical activities move which kinds of physical objects into/out of locations, (C3) relations between locations and (C4) relations between individual physical objects and batches as visualized in Fig. 1.

Applying P1-P3 on the context knowledge shown in Fig. 1 allows us to infer missing identifiers: Activities *Fill* and *Seal* process boxes at distinct locations (the *Fill* and *Seal* Station), while *physical (Un)LoadSS* and *(Un)LoadFS* activities *move* a box into/out of these locations. Physical activities *LoadAL* and *UnloadAL* move a *Tray* of boxes into/out of the *AssemblyLine* containing the locations of the *Seal* and *Fill* station. (1) From $\#_b(e_{10}) = b_1$ we know that b_1 is at the *Seal Station*; by P1, box b_1 must have been moved into/out of the *Seal Station*: $\#_b(e_9) = \#_b(e_{13}) = b_1$. (2) From $\#_b(e_{10}) = b_1$, $\#_b(e_{15}) = b_2$, $\#_b(e_{18}) = b_3$ we know that b_1, b_2, b_3 are at the *Seal Station* and thus at the *AssemblyLine*; by P1 they must have been moved into/out of the *AssemblyLine* resulting in multi-valued $\#_b(e_1) = \#_b(e_{20}) = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$. (3) Box $\#_b(e_9) = b_1$ is at location $\#_p(e_9) = 1$ in the *Tray*; from $b_1 \in \#_b(e_1) = \#_b(e_{20})$ follows that b_1 at $p = 1$ is at the *AssemblyLine* from time t_1 to t_{20} . By P2, P3 and $\#_p(e_5) = \#_p(e_7) = 1$ we know that e_5 and e_7 must have operated on the box with $p = 1$ at the fill station, resulting in $\#_b(e_7) = b_1$. (4) From $\#_b(e_5) = \#_b(e_7) = b_1$ we know that b_1 is present at the *Fill Station* from t_5 to t_7 . From P2 follows that e_6 must operate on a box present at the *Fill Station*, thus $\#_b(e_6) = b_1$. Consistently applying this reasoning infers all identifiers shown in Fig. 2(d).

Problem statement. The problem we address in this paper is how to automate the above inference of missing entity identifiers based on context knowledge of a process with physical objects. We assume as input: (I1) an event table T where each event has a timestamp, activity and the top-level location (e.g. equipment) but may not have an entity identifier, and for each real physical object in the process, there is at least one event $e \in E$ that refers to it, and (I2) context information about the process, e.g., physical constraints C1-C4 above. Given I1 and I2, we want to (O1) infer for each event the (likely) entities involved such that (O2) the resulting entity traces describe a consistent execution of the process matching the (physical) context. The latter can be validated by replaying the log on a process model, though the model itself is not a required input.

4 Inferring Entity Identifiers from Context

We now describe our method for inferring identifiers from context. We first encode the incomplete event data (I1) in an *Event Knowledge Graph* (EKG). Exploiting the flexibility of KGs, we show how to extend the EKG with context information (I2). We then define inference rules over EKGs to infer the missing identifiers (O1). While the concepts for modeling context and inference rules are generic, we demonstrate their application for the concrete problem of inferring identifiers for processes with physical objects stated in Sect. 3.

4.1 Basic Idea

We first illustrate the basic idea on how to define and use context information for inference on a part of the log of Sect. 3 repeated in Fig. 3.

The log has event e_{10} with activity *Seal* for box b_1 in equipment 3012. The physical context described in Fig. 1 shows that *Seal* occurs at the *Seal Station* within equipment 3012. The log contains events e_9 and e_{13} with activities *LoadSS* and *UnloadSS* which are not correlated to a box, i.e. $\#_b(e_9) = \#_b(e_{13}) = \perp$. Context (c.f. Fig. 1) shows that (1) activities *LoadSS* and *UnloadSS* operate on a box, thus e_9 and e_{13} have incomplete information, and (2) these activities occur at the same location as e_{10} (the *Seal Station* of equipment 3012). From principle (P1), b_1 must have been loaded into the *Seal Station* before t_{10} and unloaded from *Seal Station* after t_{10} , e_9 and e_{13} are the first preceding load event and succeeding unload event, hence $\#_b(e_9) = \#_b(e_{13}) = b_1$. Even though events e_{11} and e_{12} occur in between e_{10} and e_{13} , they are not considered simply because they occur at a different location.

Fig. 3. Example on how to infer missing entity identifiers using context information.

Fig. 3 (bottom) schematically visualizes this reasoning over the context of the events as an inference rule. On the left-hand side, only event e_{10} is correlated to b_1 (blue circle, edge to b_1) while events e_9 and e_{13} are uncorrelated (black circles); e_9 and e_{13} perform activities at the same physical location (bar labeled SS from e_9 to e_{13}) where e_9 loads an object into the location (down arrow) and e_{13} unloads an object (up arrow); e_{10} occurs time-wise between e_9 and e_{13} and performs an activity at location SS (arrow from e_{10} to SS). On the right-hand side, the correlation of e_9 and e_{13} to b_1 is inferred (blue circles, red dashed edges to b_1). In the following subsections, we discuss how to precisely define and apply such inference rules on event data.

4.2 Modeling Context in Property Graphs

The rule and its application we illustrated in Fig. 3 reasoned over events correlated to multiple entities, and their context of activities (with properties) and locations (see C1-C4 in Sect. 3). We now show how to formally model event data with such contextual information using *event knowledge graphs* (EKGs). We first recall the underlying data model of *labeled property graphs* (LPG), the specific model of EKGs, and how the incomplete log of Fig. 3 is modeled as an EKG. Afterwards, we extend the meta-model of EKGs with contextual information and define rules over these extended EKGs.

Existing Models. An LPG G is a directed multi-graph where each node and each edge of G (called relationship) is typed by one or more *labels* Lab . A node n may have multiple labels $\lambda(n) \in 2^{Lab}$; a relationship r always has one label $\lambda(r) \in Lab$. A node or relationship can carry properties, i.e., attribute-value pairs, written $\#_a(n) = v$; see [21, App. A]. We write $n \in \ell$ if $\ell \in \lambda(n)$ and $(n, n') \in \ell$ or $n \ell n'$ if r is an edge from n to n' , $\vec{r} = (n, n')$, and $\lambda(r) = \ell$.

An Event Knowledge Graph (EKG) is an LPG G with node labels **Event**, **Entity** and relationship labels **corr** (“event correlated to entity”), and **df** (“event directly followed by event”) so that (1) **Event** and **Entity** nodes are disjoint, (2) each $e \in \mathbf{Event}$ has $\#_{time}(e) \in Time$ and $\#_{act}(e) \in Act$ defined and (3) each **df**-relationship $r \in \mathbf{df}$, $\vec{r} = (e, e')$ defines that e' directly follows e from the perspective of entity $r.ent = n \in \mathbf{Entity}$.¹ The meta-model of this basic EKG is shown in Fig. 4 (red-dashed rectangle).

We work with the slightly extended meta-model shown at Fig. 4 (top) proposed in [11] which additionally defines relationships $n_1 \mathbf{rel} n_2$ between $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbf{Entity}$ and relationships $e \mathbf{observed} a$ describing that $e \in \mathbf{Event}$ executed activity $a \in \mathbf{Activity}$.

The standard EKG construction from an event table with entities creates **Event**, **Entity** and **Activity** nodes and **corr**, **df** and **observed** relationships as follows [11]: (1) each event record is translated into an **Event** node; (2) infer **entity** node n with $\#_{type}(n) = ET$ if there is an **Event** node e with $\#_{ET}(e) = n$ and

¹ Formally, let $e, e' \in \mathbf{Event}$ be correlated to the same entity $n \in \mathbf{Entity}$, $(e, n), (e', n) \in \mathbf{corr}$: $e \mathbf{df} e'$ holds iff $\#_{time}(e) < \#_{time}(e')$ and there is no other event $e'' \in \mathbf{Event}$, $(e'', n) \in \mathbf{corr}$ between e and e' , i.e. $\#_{time}(e) < \#_{time}(e'') < \#_{time}(e')$.

Fig. 4. Schematic meta-model; (a) basic EKG meta-model [10]; (b) extended meta-model; (c) extension by this work; (d) refined meta-model for use case

add $e \text{ corr } n$ (e is correlated to n); (3) infer an $n_1 \text{ rel } n_2$ relationship if there is an event node e with $e \text{ corr } n_1$ and $e \text{ corr } n_2$; (4) infer df-relationships between events correlated to the same entity node n ; (5) infer Activity nodes a with $\#_{name}(a) = act_name$ if there is an Event node e with $\#_{act}(e) = act_name$ and add $e \text{ observed } a$.

In case of incomplete information in the event table, step (2) results in incomplete correlation (*corr*) relationships and step (3) results in incomplete and false df-relationships.

Adding Context. In every process, each event is related to the activity performed and the entities involved. We therefore consider activity and entities as the natural *context* of an event, while the timestamp is local to the event itself. For a specific process, we can further detail the context of an event based on domain-knowledge of the process. For this, we have to *refine* the Entity and Activity nodes in the meta-model in larger Entity and Activity contexts (see Fig. 4 (bottom)). Next, we discuss this refinement for the processes with physical objects in our problem.

The entity context is refined by introducing a dedicated label for each entity type and for each relationship type in the process. The refined entity context of our example is shown in Fig. 4 (bottom) and defines entity labels for 3 types of entity nodes for Equipment, Box and BatchPosition and an *at_pos* relation.

The *activity context* of an event is refined by adding *more information* about the activity that is executed, i.e., by adding more related nodes that describe the activity further. Which information is added depends on the process and the required inference. For our use case, we require activity context in the form of how the activities operate on entities and their locations, see C1-C4 in Sect. 3. We introduce two additional node labels *EntityType* and *Location* and relationship labels *acts_on*, *at* and *part_of*. Each Activity acts on EntityTypes at a specific Location, e.g., *LoadSS* acts_on a *Box*. Depending on the use case, a more specific

Table 2. Records containing contextual data

Location Records		Activity Records			
name	part of	activity	label	entity type	location
AL	-	LoadAL	load	box	AL
FS	AL	UnloadAL	unload	box	AL
SS	AL	LoadFS	load	box	FS
		UnloadFS	unload	box	FS
		Fill	acts_on	box	FS
	

label instead of `acts_on` can be chosen to describe the semantics of the activity, e.g. activity *LoadSS* loads a *Box*. Further, we use `part_of` relation to express when a location l_1 is physically part of a larger location l_2 , e.g., *SS part_of AL*.

We adapt the procedure to construct an EKG with a refined entity and activity context as follows. We change to procedure to infer refined **Entity** nodes (step 2) and relationships (step 3): (2) We infer a node n with labels $\lambda(n) = \{\text{entity, ET}\}$ if there is an **Event** node e with $\#_{ET}(e) = n$; then relationship $e \text{ corr } n$ is added as usual; (3) We use the label of a refined relationship (instead of generic `rel`) between two entity nodes whenever one is defined in the schema. Adding the activity context to the EKG requires use-case specific adaptations to the procedure. Assuming context information about activities and locations is specified in tables similar to event tables (see Tab. 2), we perform the following steps after step 5: (6) For each location record l we treat $\#_{name}(l)$ as a unique identifier and create node $loc \in \text{Location}$ and set $\#_{prop}(loc) = \#_{prop}(l)$ for each $prop \in Attr$ in l . (7) Add relationship $l \text{ part_of } l'$ for $l, l' \in \text{Location}$ iff $\#_{name}(l') = \#_{part_of}(l)$. (8) We create for each unique value $et = \#_{entitytype}(r)$ in Activity records r a new node $et \in \text{EntityType}$. (9) Each Activity Record r provides details for an activity $\#_{activity}(r) = a$ that already exists as a node $a \in \text{Activity}$ in the EKG. Thus, we can link a to the location node $l = \#_{location}(r)$ created in step (6) by adding relationship $a \text{ at } l$. (10) For each activity $a = \#_{activity}(r)$ in Activity Records r , $qualifier = \#_{label}(r)$ defines how a operates on $et = \#_{entitytype}(r)$ and we add a relationship $a \text{ qualifier } et$.

Fig. 5 shows part of the EKG obtained from the incomplete log (Fig. 2) extended with **Activity** and **Location** nodes based on the records and relations in Tab. 2.

4.3 Inference Rules

We now have an EKG G extended with context information where `corr` relationships are incomplete due to missing information in the underlying event table. As `df`-relationships are unreliable due to missing `corr` relationships, we remove all `df`-relationships from G . We infer the missing `corr` relationships based on which we can compute reliable `df`-relationships. Modeling event context in an EKG enables us to infer missing `corr` relationships by defining local rules describing contextual patterns in EKGs. We first define the rules in general, then present a first example and then define the semantics of rule application on EKGs.

Fig. 5. Partial instance of the EKG

We define an inference rule as a simple graph-transformation pattern in an EKG G that defines for nodes n_1, \dots, n_r a “left-hand-side” (LHS) graph pattern specifying the context from which missing relationships can be inferred. The “right-hand side” (RHS) of the rule are then relationships from n_1, \dots, n_r to other nodes in the LHS; e.g. adding `corr` relationships between events and entities provides the missing identifiers.

More concretely, an inference rule $IR = (G, R_{inferred}, c, m)$ is an EKG G where we mark one or more relationships $R_{inferred}$ of G as the RHS, i.e., to be inferred, by setting property $\#_{RHS}(r) = True$. All other nodes and relationships of G define the LHS. Further, IR defines an *ordering condition* c and a *minimization condition* m over the properties of the nodes N in G to limit the matches of the LHS; see [21, App. A].

For example Fig. 6 describes an inference rule based on principle (P1) from Sect. 4.1. It infers the unknown entity identifiers of load and unload events f_0 and f_2 from event f_1 occurring in between f_0 and f_2 at the same location.

Fig. 6 depicts the LHS of the rule by solid edges. It defines three events ($f_0, f_1, f_2 \in Event$). The activity operation and location of each event f_i is modeled through the activity f_i observed $a_i, a_i \in Activity$. Specifically, by the relationship labels r from a_0 and a_2 to $et \in EntityType$ with $\#_{name}(et) = 'Box'$, events f_0 and f_2 observe a physical loading and unloading activity for a box. The events are observed at the same location ℓ by the relationships f_i observed a_i at $\ell, \ell \in Location, i = 1, 2, 3$. Furthermore all events are correlated to the same equipment f_i corr $eq \in Equipment, i = 1, 2, 3$, and only f_1 is correlated to box b , i.e., f_1 corr $b \in Box$ while f_0 and f_2 are not correlated to a box, i.e., $N_{incomplete} = \{f_0, f_2\}$.

Ordering condition $c: \#_{time}(f_0) \leq \#_{time}(f_1) \leq \#_{time}(f_2)$ restricts the LHS to events f_0, f_1, f_2 that follow each other in time. Minimization condition $m: minimize \#_{time}(f_2) - \#_{time}(f_0)$ restricts the LHS to only those f_0, f_2 such that

Fig. 6. Inference rule detailing the short-hand notation of Fig. 3.

no other (un)load events happen in between f_0 and f_2 . m also implies that f_0 , f_2 are the first preceding load event and first succeeding unload event w.r.t. f_1 . Note that the LHS cannot rely on *df*-relationships to express ordering of the events as *df*-relationships are incomplete due to incomplete *corr* relationships.

The RHS of the rule is $R_{inferred} = \{r_0, r_2\}$ with $\vec{r}_0 = (f_0, b)$ and $\vec{r}_2 = (f_2, b)$ (indicated by red dashed edges in Fig. 6). Subsequently, we use the notation shown in Fig. 3 as short-hand for inference rules, i.e., Fig. 3 denotes the rule of Fig. 6.

An inference rule $IR = (G, R_{inferred}, c, m)$ is *applied* on an (incomplete) EKG G' as follows. Let $LHS(IR)$ be the graph G without $R_{inferred}$. (1) An *instance* of $LHS(IR)$ is a sub-graph G'' of G' that is injectively homomorphic to $LHS(IR)$, so that the ordering condition c holds in G'' , i.e., the sub-graph G'' has all nodes, relationships, labels, and properties described in G and c except $R_{inferred}$, and possibly other relationships not described in G . (2) If the minimization condition m is defined, pick only those instances G''_1, \dots, G''_k of $LHS(IR)$ where m is minimal; otherwise pick all instances. (3) For each picked instance G''_i of $LHS(IR)$ in G' , apply IR by extending G''_i by the RHS of IR , i.e., adding the missing relationships $R_{inferred}$; see [21, App. A].

For example, $LHS(IR)$ of Fig. 6 has an instance G'' in the EKG of Fig. 5 as $LHS(IR)$ injectively maps to G'' by $f_0 \mapsto e_9, f_1 \mapsto e_{10}, f_2 \mapsto e_{13}, b \mapsto box1, eq \mapsto eqpm3012, a_0 \mapsto a_{LoadSS}, a_1 \mapsto a_{Seal}, a_2 \mapsto a_{UnloadSS}, \ell \mapsto SealStation$ and $et \mapsto et_{Box}$. Note that G'' has all nodes, labels, properties and relationships specified in $LHS(IR)$. Further, c holds in G'' as $\#time(e_9) \leq \#time(e_{10}) \leq \#time(e_{13})$. G'' also minimizes $m : \#time(e_{13}) - \#time(e_9)$. Applying the RHS adds *corr* relationships $\vec{r}_9 = (e_9, b_1)$ and $\vec{r}_{13} = (e_{13}, b_1)$.

The complete inference procedure using a set of rules $\{IR_1, \dots, IR_k\}$ on an EKG G (with added context) is: (1) remove all *df*-relationships from G , (2) repeatedly apply each IR_i until no more relationships are added to G , (3) infer the *df*-relationships (now based on complete *corr*-relationships).

5 Application and Evaluation

We now use the generic principles for extending EKGs with (use-case specific) context (see Sect. 4.2) and inference rules (see Sect. 4.3) to define concrete inference rules for the problem of inferring identifiers for physical objects defined in Sect. 3. The rules are implemented as queries over the Neo4j graph DB. We report on their use in an industrial use case.

5.1 Inference Rules

Based on the entity and activity context defined in the refined EKG meta-model of Fig. 4, we translated principles P1-P3 of Sect. 3 into five inference rules.

Inference for One Level. Fig. 7 shows two rules to infer missing entity identifiers for an object at a location L using the short-hand notation introduced in Sect. 4.1, see [21, App. C] for EKG notation. Rule A is explained in Sect. 4.1; from

an event f_1 with known identifier, we can infer the identifiers for the load and unload events f_0 and f_2 at the same location L . Rule B is simply the reverse of

Fig. 7. Rules A, B, C, D and E

Rule E also deals with events that should only be correlated to one of the objects loaded/unloaded during f_0 and f_4 . As stated before, additional information is required for correct inferences such as the relative spatial position of an object (P3). Hence, events happening at a lower-level location L correlated to position x can be related to entity b_1 at pos x that is loaded into K .

These rules allow correlating multiple entities to the same events, which allows to infer, e.g., batching, when physically possible, or reveal ambiguous context information when physically impossible.

Rule A; based on the load and unload events of a location, we infer the missing identifiers of the events happening at that location by propagating downwards. Note that any rule can correlate any number of entities to an event. For Rule A, this is desired behavior: all physical objects present at location L need to be loaded and unloaded from L . For Rule B, it depends on the context whether this is desired behavior. If f_1 should only be correlated to one of the objects loaded/unloaded during f_0 and f_2 , more information is required which will be explained in Rule E.

Inference between Entities. Rule C (Fig. 7) is derived from principle (P3); from an event f_0 associated both to a box b_1 and a batch position x , we can infer that box b_1 is at pos x in the tray.

Inference for Multiple Levels. Rules D and E of Fig. 7 use the same principles as Rule A and B respectively for locations containing other locations. As the **part of** relation is transitive, principles (P1) and (P2) can be also used to infer missing entity identifiers on higher/lower location levels via **part of** (see Fig. 4) or its transitive closure **part of***. Rule D infers missing identifiers through multiple levels by propagating upwards and Rule E downwards through multiple levels.

5.2 Implementation and Demonstration

We implemented the approach of Sect. 4 and rules A-E of Sect. 5.1 as Cypher queries over the Neo4j graph database; see [21, App. D] and https://github.com/Ava-S/EKG_Inference.

Applying the implementation on an incomplete event table of our running example infers the correlation and traces shown in Fig. 8 as follows: (1) applying Rule D propagates b_1, b_2 and b_3 from *Seal* events upwards to *LoadSS*, *UnloadSS*, *LoadAL* and *UnloadAL* events; (2) applying Rule C creates the `at_pos` relation between *Box* and *BatchPosition* nodes using *LoadSS* events which are now correlated to both these entities; (3) applying Rule E propagates entity identifiers from *(Un)LoadAL* events downwards to *LoadFS* and *UnloadFS* events; (4) applying Rule B propagates identifiers from *(Un)LoadFS* events to *Fill* events; see [21, App. B] for the full EKG after inference.

Recall that any rule can correlate any number of entities to an event. Rule D assigns multiple boxes (b_1, b_2 and b_3) to the *LoadAL* event e_1 and *UnloadAL* event e_{20} . Even though Rule D is unaware of batching events, it is still able to infer multiple identifiers to batching events. The resulting traces align with the process in Fig. 1 and the physical constraints.

LOG					
	activity	time	b	p	equipment
e_1	LoadAL	t_1			3012
e_2	LoadFS	t_2		3	3012
e_3	Fill	t_3			3012
e_4	UnloadFS	t_4		3	3012
e_5	LoadFS	t_5		1	3012
e_6	Fill	t_6			3012
e_7	UnloadFS	t_7		1	3012
e_8	LoadFS	t_8		2	3012
e_9	LoadSS	t_9		1	3012
e_{10}	Seal	t_{10}	b_1		3012
e_{11}	Fill	t_{11}			3012
e_{12}	UnloadFS	t_{12}		2	3012
e_{13}	UnloadSS	t_{13}		1	3012
e_{14}	LoadSS	t_{14}		2	3012
e_{15}	Seal	t_{15}	b_2		3012
e_{16}	UnloadSS	t_{16}		2	3012
e_{17}	LoadSS	t_{17}		3	3012
e_{18}	Seal	t_{18}	b_3		3012
e_{19}	UnloadSS	t_{19}		3	3012
e_{20}	UnloadAL	t_{20}			3012

Fig. 8. An incomplete event table of running example.

5.3 Industrial Use Case: NXP's Sawing Process

The proposed method was applied on an industrial use case; the sawing process at NXP Semiconductors (NXP). NXP is a globally operating company that designs, develops, and manufactures Integrated Circuit (IC) chips. We focus on the dicing step in which wafers are sawn into dies (unpackaged chips). The sawing equipment has several sensors installed to record the different events operating on the wafers. The collected data covered a week of manufacturing. Data inspection revealed that some entity identifiers were recorded incorrectly. These identifiers were dropped during data cleaning and needed to be inferred.

Process Description. Multiple wafers are loaded into the sawing equipment together in a rack for wafers. All wafers are then handled in parallel as follows: the wafers are aligned and cut at the cutting station, and then cleaned at the cleaning station. Finally the rack with all cut wafers is unloaded. A rack has multiple slots containing one wafer each; wafers in the same rack are distinguished by their slot position in the rack.

Table 3. Overview of the activity types and whether the wafer identifiers are present.

type	entity	wafer identifier(s)	# activities	# events
act on	wafer	✓	3	≈ 1000
act on	wafer	-	10	≈ 3100
load	(batch of) wafers	-	1	≈ 50
load	wafer	-	5	≈ 1550
unload	wafer	-	5	≈ 1550
Total			24	≈ 7250

Activities and Events. Tab. 3 gives an overview of the different activity types in NXP’s sawing process, how many activities of this type the process has and their frequency. Only 3/24 activities recorded wafer identifiers, resulting in ≈ 6250/7250 events without wafer identifier.

Inferring Missing Information. We adapted the entity and activity context in the EKG meta-model of Fig. 4 and the inference rules of Sect. 5.1 to match the NXP use case: The `Entity:Box` and `Entity:BatchPosition` nodes were replaced respectively with `Entity:Wafer` and `Entity:SlotPosition` nodes. We applied the adapted Rules A-E to infer the missing wafer identifiers. Construction of the complete EKG and inference required less than 30 seconds, resulting in 7225/7250 events correlated to at least one wafer.

Validation. We validated the correctness of the inferred identifiers through alignment-based conformance checking. A proclat reference model of the multi-entity process was created and validated with NXP [22]; the proclat describes for each entity type (e.g. wafer, rack) a life-cycle model as state machine without concurrency. The proclat model was added to the EKG by modeling `df_a` relationships between `Activity` nodes (see Fig. 4 and [11]), where `a df_a a'` describes that activity `a` can be directly followed by `a'` for a particular entity, e.g. wafer or a rack. This allowed us to measure whether all `df`-relationships of a wafer `w` form a complete trace according to the wafer life-cycle using the technique in [11, Sect 6.4]: we checked whether each `df`-relationship (e, e') of `w` has a corresponding `df_a`-relationship (a, a') for wafers with `e observed a` and `e' observed a'`. While for the extracted data, 0 wafers had a complete trace, after inference 88% had complete traces, the remaining 12% of incomplete traces were attributed to non-recorded or double-recorded events.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we studied the problem of inferring missing entity identifiers in the generalized setting of multi-entity processes (e.g., with batching) that are executed in a physical environment. We showed that the problem can be modeled and solved in Event Knowledge Graphs (EKGs) by extending an EKG over incomplete data with context information about entities and activities, and by defining inference rules over this EKG according to simple principles of physical processes. As a side-effect, the inclusion of context information and inference

rules makes EKGs “true” knowledge graphs [7]. Using inference rules over EKGs shows that missing identifiers can be inferred efficiently even when no normative control-flow model is available or applicable (e.g., in case of multi-entity processes or batching). An industrial case study proved that our technique is applicable to industrial processes both in terms of quality of inference and performance. It should be noted that the running example was constructed based on the industry use case.

While the techniques of inference rules over context-extended EKGs are generic, our study only demonstrated context representation and inference rules for multi-entity interactions in the form of batching 1:n synchronization and activities in hierarchical locations. Similar processes with incomplete information exist in healthcare, customer movement, and other production processes [8], which suggest further research on applying the proposed techniques in these domains. For processes with other forms of synchronization or activity context, more research is required to develop a generic, systematic approach for extending EKGs with context information and defining inference rules over incomplete event data. Our approach is also limited in dealing with noise. We assumed each entity identifier to be observed in at least one event and events to not deviate from the intended process. In case all identifiers are missing and we know that a particular activity only happens once for a certain entities, artificial identifiers can be generated. Additionally, in the industrial use case some unload events were not recorded, however the rules were still able to infer the missing identifiers for the preceding load events. Other forms of missing identifiers require further research. In case of deviating events, information about the intended process (i.e., process model) has to be included in the inference. Finally, the proposed inference rule mechanism is not specified to inferring corr edges, suggesting further viable research for inference by integrating event data and process knowledge beyond missing identifiers.

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A Definitions

A.1 Event Knowledge Graph

A *labeled property graph* (LPG) $G = (N, R, Attr, \#, Lab, \lambda)$ has Nodes N , relationships R , attributes $Attr$ and a partial attribute value function $\# : (N \cup R) \times Attr \rightarrow Val$, where $r \in R$ defines the edge $\vec{r} = (n_{src}, n_{tgt}) \in N \times N$. Each node $n \in N$ has labels $\lambda(n) \in 2^{Lab}$; each relationship $r \in R$ has a single label $\lambda(r) \in Lab$. We write $n \in \ell$ if $n \in N, \ell \in \lambda(n)$ and $(n, n') \in \ell$ or $n \ell n'$ if $r \in R, \vec{r} = (n, n'), \lambda(r) = \ell$.

An Event Knowledge Graph (EKG) is an LPG G with node labels **Event**, **Entity** and relationship labels **corr** (“event correlated to entity”), and **df** (“event directly followed by event”) so that

1. **Event** and **Entity** nodes are disjoint,
2. each $e \in \mathbf{Event}$ has $\#_{time}(e) \in Time$ and $\#_{act}(e) \in Act$ defined,
3. each **df**-relationship $r \in \mathbf{df}$, $\vec{r} = (e, e')$ defines that e' directly follows e from the perspective of entity $r.ent = n \in \mathbf{Entity}$, i.e., $(e, n), (e', n) \in \mathbf{corr}$ and $\#_{time}(e) < \#_{time}(e')$ and there is no other event $e'' \in \mathbf{Event}, (e'', n) \in \mathbf{corr}$ with $\#_{time}(e) < \#_{time}(e'') < \#_{time}(e')$.

A.2 Inference Rule

Formally, an *inference rule* $IR = (G, N_{incomplete}, R_{inferred}, c, m)$ has an EKG $G = (N, R, Attr, \#, Lab, \lambda)$ according to a refined meta-model (e.g. Fig. 4c). The nodes $N_{incomplete} \subseteq N$ are the nodes for which relations shall be inferred. The RHS of IR is defined by the relations $R_{inferred} \subseteq R$ with $\#_{RHS}(r) = True$, $\forall r \in R_{inferred}$ so that for each $r \in R_{inferred}$ exists $n \in N_{incomplete}$ and $m \in N$ with $\vec{r} = (n, m)$. The LHS of IR is G without $R_{inferred}$, i.e., $LHS(IR) = (N, R \setminus R_{inferred}, Attr, \#, Lab)$. Further, IR defines an *ordering condition* c and a *minimization condition* m over the properties of the nodes N in G to limit the matches of the LHS.

A.3 Application of Inference Rule

An inference rule $IR = (G, N_{incomplete}, R_{inferred}, cond)$ is *applied* on an (incomplete) EKG G' as follows. An *instance* of $LHS(IR)$ in G' is a sub-graph of G that is injectively homomorphic² to LHS , i.e., a mapping $\beta : N \mapsto N'$ from nodes of $LHS(IR)$ to nodes of G' (called *binding*) that respect the labels, properties and relationships between the nodes in N so that the ordering condition $c[N/\beta(N)]$ (replacing the variables (nodes of $LHS(IR)$) in c with the nodes of G) evaluates to true. The empty condition c always evaluates to true. Then from all instances of $LHS(IR)$, pick the instances that minimize all conditions of m . In

² Formally, we define a mapping $f : G \mapsto G'$ for $G = (N, R, Attr, \#, Lab, \lambda)$ and $G' = (N', R', Attr, \#, Lab, \lambda)$ by $f : N \mapsto N'$ where for any $u, v \in N$ holds: $f(u) = f(v) \Rightarrow u = v$ (injective), and $(u, v) \in R \Rightarrow (f(u), f(v)) \in R'$ (homomorphic).

case m is empty, all instances of $LHS(IR)$ are picked. For each minimal instance $LHS(IR)$ in G' with binding β , apply IR by extending G' by the RHS of IR , i.e., add a new relationship r^* to G' for each $r \in R_{inferred}$, $\vec{r} = (e, n)$ so that $\lambda'(r^*) = \lambda(r)$, $\vec{r}^* = (\beta(e), \beta(n))$.

B Complete EKG of Running Example

Fig. 9. Complete instance of Event Knowledge Graph after inference for the Event Table in 8(top)

C Extended Inference Rules

C.1 Rule A: propagate upwards, one level

Fig. 10. Inference Rule detailing the short-hand notation of Fig. 7 Rule A.

C.2 Rule B: propagate downwards, one level

Fig. 11. Inference Rule detailing the short-hand notation of Fig. 7 Rule B.

C.3 Rule C: Create at pos relation between entities

Fig. 12. Inference Rule detailing the short-hand notation of Fig. 7 Rule C.

C.4 Rule D: propagate upwards, multiple levels

Fig. 13. Inference Rule detailing the short-hand notation of Fig. 7 Rule D.

C.5 Rule E: propagate downwards, multiple levels

Fig. 14. Inference Rule detailing the short-hand notation of Fig. 7 Rule E.

D Queries

Rules A, B, D and E determine the load and unload events at the different location levels such that the time difference is minimized. Given that all events are recorded correctly, the constraint that the administrative event should be in between a pair of load and unload events can be relaxed by using the first preceding load event (or first succeeding unload event) w.r.t. the administrative event. With this relaxation, the inference rules are also applicable when there are only *load* events (no *unload* events). The shown queries determine the inference using the first preceding load events. The queries can be adapted without loss of generality to use the first succeeding unload events.

D.1 Rule A; propagate upwards, one level

```

1 MATCH (f1: Event) - [:CORR] -> (b: Box)
2 MATCH (f1) - [:CORR] -> (equipment: Equipment)
3 MATCH (f1) - [:OBSERVED] -> (a1: Activity) - [:AT] -> (l: Location)
4 WITH f1, l, equipment, b
5 CALL {WITH f1, l, equipment
6     // ensure f0 is a load event operating on a box
7     MATCH (f0: Event) - [:OBSERVED] -> (a0: Activity)
8     - [:LOADS] -> (:EntityType {name: 'Box'})
9     MATCH (a0) - [:AT] -> (l)
10    MATCH (f0) - [:CORR] -> (equipment)
11    WHERE f0.timestamp <= f1.timestamp
12    RETURN f0 as f0_first_preceding // find the first preceding f0
13    ORDER BY f0.timestamp DESC LIMIT 1}
14 MERGE (f0_first_preceding) - [:CORR] -> (b)
    
```

D.2 Rule B; propagate downwards, one level

```

1 MATCH (f1: Event) - [:CORR] -> (equipment: Equipment)
2 MATCH (f1) - [:OBSERVED] -> (a1: Activity) -[:AT]-> (l: Location)
3 // ensure activity of f1 (a1) should operate on a box, the specific operation is undefined
4 WITH f1, equipment, l
5 MATCH (a1) --> (:EntityType {name: 'Box'})
6 CALL {WITH f1, equipment, l
7     // ensure f0 is a load event operating on a box
8     MATCH (f0: Event)-[:OBSERVED]->(a0: Activity)
9     - [:LOADS] -> (:EntityType {name: 'Box'})
10    MATCH (a0) - [:AT] -> (l)
11    MATCH (f0)-[:CORR]->(equipment)
12    WHERE f0.timestamp <= f1.timestamp
13    RETURN f0 as f0_first_prec // find the first preceding f0
14    ORDER BY f0.timestamp DESC LIMIT 1
15 }
16 // only merge when f0_first_prec is actually related to a Box
17 WITH f1, [(f0_first_prec)-[:CORR]->(b: Box) | b] as related_b
18 FOREACH (b in related_b |
19     MERGE (f1) - [:CORR] -> (b)
20 )
    
```

D.3 Rule C: create at pos relation between entities

```

1 MATCH (e: Event) - [:CORR] -> (b: Box)
2 MATCH (e) - [:CORR] -> (bp: BatchPosition)
3 MERGE (b) - [:AT_POS] -> (bp)
    
```

D.4 Rule D: propagate upwards, multiple levels

```

1  MATCH (f2: Event) - [:CORR] -> (b: Box)
2  MATCH (f2) - [:CORR] -> (equipment: Equipment)
3  MATCH (f2) - [:OBSERVED] -> (a2: Activity)
4  - [:AT] -> (l: Location) - [:PART_OF*0..] -> (k: Location)
5  WITH f2, k, equipment, b
6  CALL {WITH f2, k, equipment
7      // ensure f0 is a load event operating on a box
8      MATCH (f0: Event) - [:OBSERVED] -> (a0: Activity)
9      - [:LOADS] -> (:EntityType {name: 'Box'})
10     MATCH (a0) - [:AT] -> (k)
11     MATCH (f0) - [:CORR] -> (equipment)
12     WHERE f0.timestamp <= f1.timestamp
13     // find the first preceding f0
14     RETURN f0 as f0_first_preceding
15     ORDER BY f0.timestamp DESC LIMIT 1}
16  MERGE (f0_first_preceding) - [:CORR] -> (b)

```

Note that Rule A is also applied when Rule D is applied, then there are zero part of relationships and $l = k$.

D.5 Rule E: propagate downwards multiple levels

```

1  MATCH (f2: Event) - [:CORR] -> (bp: BatchPosition)
2  MATCH (f2) -[:CORR] -> (equipment: Equipment)
3  MATCH (f2) -[:OBSERVED] -> (a2: Activity)
4  -[:AT]-> (l: Location) -[:PART_OF*0..] ->(k: Location)
5  // ensure activity of f2 (a2) should operate on a box, the specific operation is undefined
6  MATCH (a2) --> (:EntityType {name: 'Box'})
7  WITH f2, equipment, l, bp
8  CALL {WITH f2, equipment ,l
9      // ensure f0 is a load event operating on a box
10     MATCH (f0: Event)-[:OBSERVED]->(a0: Activity)
11     -[:LOADS] -> (:EntityType {name: 'Box'})
12     MATCH (a0) -[:AT] -> (k)
13     MATCH (f0) -[:CORR]->(equipment)
14     WHERE f0.timestamp <= f2.timestamp
15     // find the first preceding f0
16     RETURN f0 as f0_first_prec
17     ORDER BY f0.timestamp DESC LIMIT 1
18  }
19  // only merge when f0_first_prec is actually related to a Box
20  WITH f2, [(f0_first_prec) -[:CORR]-> (b: Box) -[:AT_POS] -> (bp) | b] as related_b
21  FOREACH (b in related_b |
22     MERGE (f2) -[:CORR] -> (b)
23  )

```